

A heuristic model for IFOV depointing phase errors

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The combination of the following three errors:

- a telescope defocus by Δx
- a relay optics defocus by $\Delta x'$
- a longitudinal IFOV depointing by $\Delta \eta$

in general results in a phase shift of the modulated signal, corresponding to a certain apparent shift ($\delta \eta$) of the star position in the longitudinal direction.

The effect can be understood, and to some extent quantitatively predicted, by means of the following model.

Let $f = 1.4$ m be the focal length of the telescope and $f' = mf$ the effective focal length at the detector ($m = 0.442$ is the relay optics magnification). If $D = 0.29$ m is the pupil diameter, then the geometrical size of the star image on the photocathode is

$$d = D \cdot \Delta x' / f' \quad (1)$$

If the telescope is well focussed ($\Delta x = 0$), then the whole image on the detector is modulated at the same phase (cf. the classical knife-edge test). But if $\Delta x \neq 0$, then there will be a phase shift between different parts of the image. This can be quantified as follows. A telescope defocus by Δx corresponds to a spherical wavefront error by:

$$WFE = \Delta x \cdot (y^2 + z^2) / (2f^2) \quad (2)$$

where (y, z) are coordinates in the pupil plane ($y^2 + z^2 \leq D^2/4$). A ray through the point (y, z) in the pupil plane has the longitudinal ray aberration

$$\delta \eta = \partial WFE / \partial y = \Delta x \cdot y / f^2 \quad (3)$$

This ray hits the detector at coordinate $y' = (d/D) \cdot y$ (in linear measure), corresponding to the angle $\eta = y' / f'$ on the sky.

If we consider first a very small IFOV (much smaller than d), then we find that the IFOV depointing angle $\Delta \eta$ will sample the ray with pupil coordinate $y = (D/d) \cdot f' \cdot \Delta \eta = m^2 f^2 \Delta \eta / \Delta x'$. The aberration of this ray is, according to (3),

$$\delta \eta = m^2 (\Delta x / \Delta x') \cdot \Delta \eta \quad (4)$$

Thus we find a simple proportionality between the longitudinal IFOV depointing ($\Delta \eta$) and the resulting image shift ($\delta \eta$); the constant of proportionality is e.g. for $\Delta x = 15 \mu\text{m}$, $\Delta x' = 250 \mu\text{m}$:

$$m^2 (\Delta x / \Delta x') \approx 0.01$$

For arbitrary IFOV profile, the effective $\delta\eta$ can be computed as the weighted average of (3) over the pupil (y,z) , with the weight taken proportional to the displaced IFOV profile at the corresponding points (y',z') on the detector.

If the IFOV is taken to be perfectly sharp and of diameter $110\ \mu\text{m}$, we find (with some approximations for the evaluation of the effective $\delta\eta$) the phase shift according to the figure below.

The resulting phase shift is zero for $|\Delta\eta| < \frac{1}{2}(\Phi - d)/f'$, provided that the IFOV diameter $\Phi > d$. This gives the central plateaux for $\Delta x' = 50$ and $150\ \mu\text{m}$ ($d = 23$ and $70\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively). The maximum possible shift is 228 milli-arcsec, corresponding to the ray aberration at $Y = \pm D/2$.

It can be noted that the maximum slope near $\Delta\eta = 0$ is obtained when the pupil image matches the IFOV in size, $\Phi = d$, which is the case for $\Delta x' = 235\ \mu\text{m}$. This is the worst possible value of $\Delta x'$ from the point of view of possible systematic astrometric errors.

Relay optics defocus - heuristic phase error model

